

Managing Editor's Column

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Here is another issue of J.UCS that is a nice mixture of topics and countries of origin of the authors: the authors come, in alphabetical order, from Australia (1), Brazil (2), Germany (3), Malaysia (1), Spain (3), Switzerland (1), UK (1) and Uruguay (1).

So...I'm certain everyone will find something of interest!

Also, let me point out two very special items:

First, in 2009 we have had a record of about 9 million hits on J.UCS and 970.000 visitors, with a readership of over 80.000. This is again an increase over the previous year. We are now preparing a RRS channel which will make it easier for readers to be alerted each time a new issue has been published.

Second, we have a conference around August 31, 2010 in Graz/Austria with very high calibre speakers, all three editors-in-chief and a number of J.UCS Editors attending. Hence we are planning a meeting of all interested in J.UCS in the afternoon of August 31. Please have a look at <http://www.the-academy-of-europe.org/10-04-02-Graz-Conf-RTF-status.pdf> and if you intend to participate in a J.UCS meeting---to find out plans for the future and to be able to tell us what you would like to be seen improved in J.UCS---, please send me an email to hmaurer@iicm.edu.

Happy reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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